

Competency-Based Digital Forensics Taxonomy for Specified Digital Forensics Occupations

A Reference Document for the Competency-Based Knowledge and Skills Requirements for Digital Evidence First Responders, Digital Forensic Technicians, and Digital Forensic Scientists

Author: Jason Jordaan

Security and Networks Research Group

Rhodes University, South Africa

ORCID: 0000-0003-0553-0345

Developed from doctoral research completed at Rhodes University (2025)

Jordaan, J. (2025). *A Digital Forensics Occupation and Competency Level Based Taxonomy: A Prerequisite for the Professionalisation of Digital Forensics* (Doctoral dissertation). Rhodes University.

Full dataset available at: <https://github.com/DFSJasonJ/JRUPhD>

© 2025 Jason Jordaan. This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International Licence (CC BY-SA 4.0). To view a copy of this licence, visit <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/>

1. Introduction and Purpose

This document presents the Competency-Based Digital Forensics Taxonomy for Specified Digital Forensics Occupations, developed through doctoral research at Rhodes University (2025). It constitutes a standalone reference instrument, designed to be accessible to practitioners, educators, curriculum designers, certification bodies, laboratory accreditation assessors, employers, and legal professionals who require a structured and authoritative specification of what digital forensics practitioners need to know and at what cognitive depth.

The taxonomy was developed through two principal research activities. First, a general digital forensics taxonomy was developed through an inductive qualitative analysis of a comprehensive corpus of governmental, professional, and academic literature, producing a consolidated, technology-agnostic body of knowledge comprising seven core knowledge areas, 23 secondary knowledge areas, and 225 unique knowledge topic statements. Second, a three-round Delphi study involving 18 international digital forensics experts was conducted to corroborate the knowledge requirements and assign minimum Bloom's revised taxonomy cognitive competency levels to each knowledge topic for each of three defined digital forensic occupations.

The full methodology, including the literature analysis process, ATLAS.ti coding procedure, Delphi study design, and statistical outcomes, is described in the published thesis. This document presents the resulting taxonomy in full, occupation by occupation and knowledge area by knowledge area, as a practical reference for use in the contexts described above.

3. How to Use This Document

3.1 Defined Terms

The following terms appear in capitalised form throughout the taxonomy and carry the definitions stated below. These definitions are deliberately broad to ensure the taxonomy remains technology-agnostic and applicable across current and future technologies.

COMPUTER: Any electronic programmable device used, whether by itself or as part of a computer system, to perform predetermined arithmetic, logical, routing, processing or storage operations. This encompasses laptop and desktop computers, servers, tablets, mobile phones, drones, CCTV systems, embedded systems, operational technology, and any other device meeting this description.

DATA STORAGE MEDIUM: Any device from which data or a computer program is capable of being reproduced or on which data or a computer program is capable of being stored. This encompasses magnetic platter hard drives, solid-state drives, RAM, flash memory, magnetic tape, optical media, cloud storage, and all other storage types.

COMPUTER SYSTEM: One computer, or two or more inter-connected or related computers, where these computers can exchange data or any other function with each other. This encompasses the Internet, physical and wireless networks, cloud services, IoT systems, and all other networked computing environments.

TRAFFIC DATA: Data relating to a communication indicating the communication's origin, destination, route, format, time, date, size, duration, or type. This encompasses all data in transit between computers within a computer system, and all transactional records or metadata relating to communications.

DATA STRUCTURE: Various file types within a computer, data storage medium, or computer system; data packets with traffic data; or substructures in any of these, having a distinctive structure designed by software developers and standards bodies. This encompasses file formats, protocol data structures, and structured data strings.

3.2 Bloom's Revised Taxonomy Levels

Bloom's revised taxonomy levels are used in this document as expressions of minimum professional cognitive demand, not as educational attainment objectives. Each level specifies the cognitive depth at which a practitioner must be able to engage with a knowledge topic in order to practise safely, effectively, and defensibly within their defined occupational role.

Level	Label	DF Verb	Professional Cognitive Meaning
1	Remember	Define	Recall relevant knowledge from long-term memory. Practitioner can identify, name, and list key concepts in the domain.
2	Understand	Explain	Make sense of learned material. Practitioner can explain how things work and why they matter in a forensic context.
3	Apply	Apply	Use knowledge in new operational situations. Practitioner can execute procedures correctly across different case circumstances.
4	Analyse	Evaluate	Break a concept into its parts; understand relationships; make independent decisions in operational practice.
5	Evaluate	Critique	Make judgements based on professional and scientific standards; select between options and justify decisions.
6	Create	Synthesise	Produce new or original work; synthesise findings into expert conclusions; develop or validate methodologies.

3.3 Reading the Taxonomy Tables

Each knowledge area section contains a table with the following columns:

KA: The core knowledge area code (e.g., CSE, APL).

Sub: The secondary knowledge area code within the core knowledge area (e.g., NLE, COH).

No.: The unique sequential number of the knowledge topic, as assigned in the general digital forensics taxonomy.

Knowledge Topic Statement: The technology-agnostic knowledge topic statement as it appears in the general digital forensics taxonomy.

BT Level: The Bloom's revised taxonomy level (1-6) representing the minimum cognitive demand required of the practitioner in this occupation for this knowledge topic.

BT Cognitive Demand: The Bloom's revised taxonomy level label (Remember, Understand, Apply, Analyse, Evaluate, Create).

BT Verb: The operational verb associated with the Bloom's level for digital forensics practice.

A knowledge topic that does not appear in an occupation's table is not applicable to that occupation. The level assignments represent the minimum required for safe and defensible practice; higher proficiency is always acceptable.

4. Occupation Definitions

Code	Occupation	Scope of Responsibility	Activity Type	Knowledge Areas
DEFR	Digital Evidence First Responder	Collection and preservation of digital evidence only	Technical	CSE, APL, FSC, SAS, FAQ
DFT	Digital Forensic Technician	Collection, preservation, and extraction of digital evidence	Technical	CSE, APL, FSC, SAS, FAQ, FEX, FAN
DFS	Digital Forensic Scientist	Collection, preservation, extraction, analysis, and interpretation; may provide expert opinion evidence in court	Technical and Scientific	CSE, APL, FSC, SAS, FAQ, FEX, FAN

5. Knowledge Area Overview

Code	Knowledge Area	Secondary Knowledge Areas	Topics	DEFR	DFT	DFS
CSE	Computer Science and Engineering	Computing hardware, storage, file systems, operating systems, databases, programming, cryptography, networking, Internet, email, virtualisation and cloud	70	✓	✓	✓
APL	Applied Law	Substantive law, procedural law, law of evidence, international law, testifying	12	✓	✓	✓
FSC	Forensic Science	Forensic principles, scientific reasoning, ethics, minimising bias, documentation, communication, quality assurance, validation, criminology	30	✓	✓	✓
SAS	Search and Seizure	Evidence identification, documentation, evidence integrity	14	✓	✓	✓
FAQ	Forensic Acquisition	Acquisition standards, digital evidence formats, media preparation, evidence integrity, live and dead-box acquisition, bypassing authentication	20	✓	✓	✓

Code	Knowledge Area	Secondary Knowledge Areas	Topics	DEFR	DFT	DFS
FEX	Forensic Examination	Investigation, examination standards, triage, data recovery, data searching and parsing, identification	63	X	✓	✓
FAN	Forensic Analysis	Forensic analysis standards, scientific methods, evaluation methods, reconstruction and attribution	12	X	✓*	✓

Digital Evidence First Responder (DEFR)

Responsible for the collection and preservation of data containing potential digital evidence in a forensically sound and legal manner.

DEFR Computer Science and Engineering (45 topics)

Foundational knowledge of computing hardware, storage, file systems, operating systems, databases, programming, cryptography, networking, and related technologies.

KA	Sub	No.	Knowledge Topic Statement	BT Level	BT Cognitive Demand	BT Verb
CSE	COH	007	The purpose and function of computer hardware, including motherboards, processors, RAM, storage devices, GPUs, input devices, output devices, heat sinks, cooling systems, and power supplies.	1 Remember	Remember	Define
CSE	COH	009	Main Memory, RAM, the stack, the heap, instructions vs. data, execution, debugging, memory cache on secondary storage devices.	1 Remember	Remember	Define
CSE	COH	010	Input/output mechanisms and devices (Peripherals, Network Interface Cards, Data Storage, etc).	1 Remember	Remember	Define
CSE	STH	012	The structure and function of physical storage devices (electromechanical magnetic drives, optical drives, magnetic tape, flash storage, and solidstate drives), storage arrays such as RAID, drive controllers, common problems and failures with physical storage devices.	2 Understand	Understand	Explain
CSE	STH	013	Data storage structures on physical storage devices (sectors).	1 Remember	Remember	Define
CSE	STH	014	The purpose of partitions on storage media, partition types (primary and extended), partition data structures (individuals structures and systems areas in various common partition schemes used by computers, mobile devices, embedded systems, and operational technology).	1 Remember	Remember	Define
CSE	STH	015	The difference between physical disks and logical volumes.	2 Understand	Understand	Explain
CSE	STH	016	Data structures of partition tables, Master Boot Records, and GUID Partition Tables (GPT).	2 Understand	Understand	Explain
CSE	STH	017	The purpose and function of storage media formatting.	2 Understand	Understand	Explain
CSE	BPR	018	The purpose and function of BIOS and UEFI, boot order, POST, secure boot.	2 Understand	Understand	Explain
CSE	BPR	019	The purpose and function of a Volume Boot Record (VBR), and the data structure of a VBR.	2 Understand	Understand	Explain
CSE	FIS	020	The purpose of file systems, and the structure of common file systems (such as FAT, FAT32, exFAT, NTFS, EXT3, EXT4, HFS, HFS+, APFS and AFS) and their individual file system elements (and the types of data stored in each).	2 Understand	Understand	Explain

KA	Sub	No.	Knowledge Topic Statement	BT Level	BT Cognitive Demand	BT Verb
CSE	FIS	021	The purpose and function of partitions/volumes in files systems.	2 Understand	Understand	Explain
CSE	FIS	022	File system metadata structures that keep track of files and directories and changes to these structures, as well as the data structures of each of these structures, including MACB times of files and folders.	2 Understand	Understand	Explain
CSE	FIS	023	Logical data storage structures (clusters), and the meaning of allocated and unallocated clusters.	2 Understand	Understand	Explain
CSE	FIS	024	Changes to file system data structures when a file or folder is saved onto the volume, or when a file or folder is deleted from the volume, and what happens at both a sector and cluster level.	1 Remember	Remember	Define
CSE	FIS	025	Partition slack, volume slack, file slack, and RAM slack.	1 Remember	Remember	Define
CSE	FIS	027	The purpose and functions of an operating system, including the kernel, processes, hardware and software interrupts, boot loaders, and BIOS.	1 Remember	Remember	Define
CSE	FIS	028	The differences between laptop and desktop operating systems, server operating systems, mobile device operating systems, operational technology (OT) operating systems, and embedded device operating systems.	1 Remember	Remember	Define
CSE	FIS	029	The purpose and function of an operating systems folder structure, the types of files that compose the operating system and their function and purpose.	1 Remember	Remember	Define
CSE	FIS	031	The purpose and function of user group, user and system accounts, file and folder permissions and the types thereof, and file and folder flags.	1 Remember	Remember	Define
CSE	FIS	034	The purpose and function of files and folders, and types of files and folders, including the data structures of these (including file headers, file footers, and other internal data structures such as file metadata).	1 Remember	Remember	Define
CSE	OSA	036	The purpose and function of backup systems and types and formats, including full backups, incremental backups, and the data structures thereof.	2 Understand	Understand	Explain
CSE	OSA	037	The concept of file fragmentation, how file fragmentation is tracked, and operating system mechanisms that manage file fragmentation.	1 Remember	Remember	Define
CSE	OSA	038	The purpose and function of servers (including web servers, DNS servers, DHCP servers, log servers, print servers, proxy servers, and database servers).	1 Remember	Remember	Define
CSE	OSA	044	The purpose and function of cryptography (plaintext and ciphertext, encryption and decryption, algorithms and cryptanalysis, key, keyspace and bruteforce, work factor, encryption systems).	1 Remember	Remember	Define
CSE	CRS	045	Encryption methods (encryption vs. encoding, symmetric encryption, asymmetric encryption, hashing).	1 Remember	Remember	Define
CSE	CRS	047	The purpose and function of hashing, one way hash algorithms, and hash collisions.	2 Understand	Understand	Explain
CSE	CRS	048	The purpose and function of authentication mechanisms (passwords, tokens, bio-metrics, two-factor authentication, dual-factor authentication, multifactor authentication).	1 Remember	Remember	Define

KA	Sub	No.	Knowledge Topic Statement	BT Level	BT Cognitive Demand	BT Verb
CSE	CRS	051	The purpose and function of firewalls, intrusion detection systems, and intrusion prevention systems.	1 Remember	Remember	Define
CSE	CRS	053	The purpose and function of networks (including network topologies, switches, hubs, routers, network interface cards, MAC addresses, IP addresses, data packets, packet headers, protocols and ports, IP4, IP6, network address translation, subnets).	1 Remember	Remember	Define
CSE	NET	055	The purpose and function of wired network connectivity, and the mechanisms used to enable connectivity.	1 Remember	Remember	Define
CSE	INT	057	The nature and structure of the Internet.	1 Remember	Remember	Define
CSE	NET	058	The structure of the World Wide Web, the purpose and function of web servers (including HTTP, HTML, Javascript, PHP, and cookies).	1 Remember	Remember	Define
CSE	NET	059	The purpose and function of Internet browsers, files associated with Internet browsers, and the data structures of these files.	1 Remember	Remember	Define
CSE	NET	060	The purpose and function of Internet search engines (including search methodologies and techniques).	1 Remember	Remember	Define
CSE	EMC	061	The purpose and function of email (including email servers, SMTP, POP3, IMAP, MIME, email spoofing, SPF, DKIM, and DMARC).	1 Remember	Remember	Define
CSE	EMC	062	The data structures of email.	1 Remember	Remember	Define
CSE	EMC	063	The purpose and function of messaging services, and the data structures thereof.	1 Remember	Remember	Define
CSE	EMC	064	The purpose and function of video and audio communication services, and the data structures thereof.	1 Remember	Remember	Define
CSE	VIC	065	The purpose and function of virtualisation (including the role of the hypervisor and the differences between Type 1 and Type 2 hypervisors).	1 Remember	Remember	Define
CSE	VIC	066	Virtual machine files, file format, and data structures of those files.	2 Understand	Understand	Explain
CSE	VIC	067	The purpose and function of cloud computing, including classes of cloud services (IaaS, PaaS, SaaS).	1 Remember	Remember	Define
CSE	VIC	068	The data structures used by cloud storage (file storage, block storage, object storage).	2 Understand	Understand	Explain
CSE	VIC	069	The purpose and function of containers, and the data structures thereof.	1 Remember	Remember	Define

DEFR Applied Law (12 topics)

Legal knowledge applicable to digital forensics practice, including substantive law, procedural law, the law of evidence, international law, and testifying as an expert witness.

KA	Sub	No.	Knowledge Topic Statement	BT Level	BT Cognitive Demand	BT Verb
APL	SBL	070	Cybercrime laws (jurisdiction dependent).	1 Remember	Remember	Define
APL	SBL	071	Data privacy laws (jurisdiction dependent).	1 Remember	Remember	Define
APL	SBL	072	Data interception laws (jurisdiction dependent).	1 Remember	Remember	Define
APL	SBL	073	Data retention laws (jurisdiction dependent).	1 Remember	Remember	Define
APL	SBL	074	Regulatory requirements for the practice of digital forensics (jurisdiction dependent).	2 Understand	Understand	Explain
APL	SBL	075	Criminal procedure law relating to the securing, preservation, and use of digital evidence (jurisdiction dependent).	2 Understand	Understand	Explain
APL	SBL	076	Civil procedure law relating to the securing, preservation, and use of digital evidence (jurisdiction dependent).	2 Understand	Understand	Explain
APL	LAE	077	The law of evidence in relation to types of evidence; admissibility and relevance of evidence; evidence integrity, the best evidence rules; and exculpatory and inculpatory evidence (jurisdiction dependent).	2 Understand	Understand	Explain
APL	LAE	078	Legal privilege.	1 Remember	Remember	Define
APL	LAE	079	International law relating to digital evidence and cybercrime, including how to legally obtain evidence in other jurisdictions.	1 Remember	Remember	Define
APL	TES	080	Testifying in court as a witness or expert witness, including techniques and methods to present digital evidence and the findings from digital forensics effectively, and methods and techniques to be an effective witness.	2 Understand	Understand	Explain
APL	TES	081	The obligations of an expert witness.	1 Remember	Remember	Define

DEFR Forensic Science (30 topics)

Forensic principles, scientific reasoning, ethics, minimising bias, documentation, communication, quality assurance, validation, and criminology.

KA	Sub	No.	Knowledge Topic Statement	BT Level	BT Cognitive Demand	BT Verb
FSC	FPR	082	The purpose and function of forensic science as a scientific field: activity and presence produce traces that are vectors of information; scene investigation is a scientific and diagnostic endeavour requiring scientific expertise; forensic science is case-based and reliant on scientific knowledge, investigative methodology and logical reasoning; forensic science is an assessment of findings in context due to time asymmetry; forensic science deals with a continuum of uncertainties; forensic science has multi-dimensional purposes and contributions; forensic science findings acquire meaning in context.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
FSC	FPR	083	The purpose and function of digital forensics (the definition of digital forensics, the digital forensics process in terms of ISO 27043).	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
FSC	FPR	084	Identification of the scope, purpose and objectives of an investigation; the ongoing review of these as the investigation progresses; and the identification of further investigative opportunities.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
FSC	FPR	085	The identification of appropriate sources of information and evidence to advance an investigation.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
FSC	FPR	086	The fragility of digital evidence.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
FSC	FPR	087	The purpose and function of a trace.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
FSC	FPR	088	The purpose, function and applicability of the Locard Principle.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
FSC	SCR	091	The scientific method.	2 Understand	Understand	Explain
FSC	SCR	092	The purpose and function of a hypothesis, and methods and techniques to develop and test hypotheses.	2 Understand	Understand	Explain
FSC	SCR	093	The importance of abductive reasoning, and abductive reasoning methods and techniques.	2 Understand	Understand	Explain
FSC	SCR	094	The importance of deductive reasoning, and deductive reasoning methods and techniques.	2 Understand	Understand	Explain
FSC	SCR	095	The importance of inductive reasoning, and inductive reasoning methods and techniques.	2 Understand	Understand	Explain
FSC	SCR	096	The Cognitive Task Model (Bottom-Up Processes, Top-Down Processes, the Foraging Loop, the Sense-Making Loop, Data Extraction vs. Analysis vs. Legal Interpretation).	2 Understand	Understand	Explain
FSC	ETH	097	The principles of ethical conduct for forensic work, including avoiding conflict of interest, objectivity, and impartiality.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
FSC	ETH	098	Principles of ethics applicable to digital forensics.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply

KA	Sub	No.	Knowledge Topic Statement	BT Level	BT Cognitive Demand	BT Verb
FSC	ETH	099	Remaining within the levels of one's competency and knowledge.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
FSC	MBI	100	The importance of objectivity, and methods and techniques to maintain objectivity.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
FSC	SCR	101	The importance of minimising bias, and methods and techniques to identify and counter potential bias.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
FSC	SCR	102	The purpose and format of contemporaneous notes during the entire forensic process (from scene to court), including documenting all decisions, actions, options and the rationale related to all lines of enquiry.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
FSC	SCR	103	Writing technical reports and affidavits to document findings. The structural requirements of digital forensic reports and affidavits.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
FSC	SCR	104	How to ensure and maintain effective communication in an investigation team, to ensure the optimal digital forensics approach and maximise the available digital evidence available, and the analysis thereof. This includes information gathering, classification and dissemination.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
FSC	COM	105	Communicating technical and scientific data, including concepts and processes, in an easy-to-understand manner, and understanding the standard terminology used in these communications.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
FSC	COM	106	Methods and techniques to be able to effectively interview witnesses and persons of interest.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
FSC	QUA	107	Methods and techniques to perform quality assurance.	1 Remember	Remember	Define
FSC	QUA	108	The purpose and function of ISO17020 and ISO17025.	1 Remember	Remember	Define
FSC	VER	109	The purpose and function of testing, validating and verification of digital forensic tools, processes, and procedures; and the methods and techniques to test, validate and verify these.	1 Remember	Remember	Define
FSC	CRI	110	Motivations of cybercriminals.	1 Remember	Remember	Define
FSC	COM	111	Types and categories of cybercriminals (lone actors, groups, gangs and syndicates, organised crime groups, hacktivist groups, terrorist groups, nation-states).	1 Remember	Remember	Define
FSC	CRI	112	The overlap between cybercrime and other crimes, and how these other crimes can facilitate cybercrime and vice versa.	2 Understand	Understand	Explain
FSC	CRI	113	The purpose and function of modus operandi.	2 Understand	Understand	Explain

DEFR Search and Seizure (14 topics)

Methods and techniques for identifying, documenting, handling, and preserving digital evidence at scenes, including evidence integrity and chain of custody.

KA	Sub	No.	Knowledge Topic Statement	BT Level	BT Cognitive Demand	BT Verb
SAS	EVI	114	Physical scene search techniques and methods.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
SAS	EVI	115	The identification of types of COMPUTERS, DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS, or COMPUTER SYSTEMS that contain digital data.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
SAS	EVI	116	The identification of other physical evidence at the physical scene that may assist the digital forensics process, such as documents containing potential passwords.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
SAS	EVI	117	The types of physical trace evidence that can exist on COMPUTERS, DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS, or COMPUTER SYSTEMS, such as fingerprints or DNA.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
SAS	EVI	118	Physical scene documentation techniques, including sketching and mapping, video recording, photography.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
SAS	EIN	119	Techniques to document the current state, condition and configuration of any COMPUTERS, DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS, or COMPUTER SYSTEMS to be seized, including photography, videography, uses of labels and photographic scales, and contemporaneous notes.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
SAS	EIN	120	Methods to secure physical scenes to ensure the safety of persons at the scene, and prevent damage to or interference with the COMPUTERS, DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS, COMPUTER SYSTEMS, or TRAFFIC DATA at the scene.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
SAS	EIN	121	Techniques to handle and collect COMPUTERS, DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS, or COMPUTER SYSTEMS in a manner that preserves potential trace evidence such as DNA and fingerprints.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
SAS	EIN	122	Techniques used to booby-trap COMPUTERS, DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS, or COMPUTER SYSTEMS, identification techniques and handling of potentially booby-trapped devices.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
SAS	EIN	123	Methods to safeguard COMPUTERS, DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS, or COMPUTER SYSTEMS that may contain data, including physical, wireless, and cellular network isolation.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
SAS	EIN	124	Methods to preserve power to powered on COMPUTERS, DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS, or COMPUTER SYSTEMS, during seizure and transport, where the device cannot be powered off due to the risk of losing data.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
SAS	EIN	125	Methods to correctly and safely power off COMPUTERS, DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS, or COMPUTER SYSTEMS during seizure.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
SAS	EIN	126	Techniques to securely package COMPUTERS, DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS, or COMPUTER SYSTEMS to preserve the evidential integrity of the device.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
SAS	EIN	127	Techniques to securely transport COMPUTERS, DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS, or COMPUTER SYSTEMS and prevent damage to, or contamination of the COMPUTERS, DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS, or COMPUTER SYSTEMS, or the destruction of trace evidence.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply

DEFR Forensic Acquisition (20 topics)

Methods and techniques for forensically preserving digital data from all categories of computers, data storage media, and computer systems.

KA	Sub	No.	Knowledge Topic Statement	BT Level	BT Cognitive Demand	BT Verb
FAQ	AQS	128	ISO 27037 guidelines for identification, collection, acquisition and preservation of digital evidence.	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate
FAQ	AQS	129	Digital evidence preservation and extraction methods, including physical (every single bit), volume (contents of a volume), file system (all file system data available for extraction), and logical (specific files and directories), and the suitability of each method based on case circumstances, and the advantages and disadvantages of each method.	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate
FAQ	DEF	130	Digital evidence formats used to preserve data from COMPUTERS, DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS, or COMPUTER SYSTEMS, including raw disk images, forensic image files, forensic copies, backups etc, and the advantages and disadvantages of each.	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate
FAQ	DEF	223	Data structure of common forensic image file formats, such as EWF, AFF, etc.	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate
FAQ	AQS	131	Methods and techniques to sterilise DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS used for storing digital evidence, and how to mathematically verify the sterilisation.	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate
FAQ	EIN	132	Methods and techniques to verify the integrity of preserved digital evidence formats through oneway cryptographic hashing (MD5, SHA1, SHA256, etc.) and thorough documentation.	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate
FAQ	EIN	133	The purpose and function of write blocking for DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS.	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate
FAQ	EIN	134	Methods and techniques for hardware write blocking for DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS, and the advantages and disadvantages thereof.	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate
FAQ	EIN	135	Methods and techniques for software write blocking for DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS, and the advantages and disadvantages thereof.	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate
FAQ	EIN	136	Order of volatility of data, and the importance of acquiring the most volatile data in the best order on COMPUTERS and COMPUTER SYSTEMS.	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate
FAQ	EIN	137	The impact on COMPUTERS, DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS, or COMPUTER SYSTEMS, including RAM and file system changes, when accessing these while they are powered on, and techniques to minimise this impact.	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate
FAQ	EIN	138	Methods and techniques to preserve a memory image or other volatile data from RAM or other volatile storage on a powered on COMPUTER or COMPUTER SYSTEM, and the advantages and disadvantages of each method.	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate
FAQ	EIN	139	Methods and techniques to identify volume or disk encryption on DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS on a powered on COMPUTER, and the importance of obtaining a logical image of the unencrypted data before powering down the COMPUTER, and the advantages and disadvantages of each method.	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate
FAQ	BPA	140	Methods and techniques to preserve data in an appropriate digital evidence format from DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS on a powered on COMPUTER, and the advantages and disadvantages of each method.	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate
FAQ	BPA	141	Methods and techniques to preserve TRAFFIC DATA in an appropriate digital evidence format from COMPUTER SYSTEMS, and the advantages and disadvantages of each method.	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate

KA	Sub	No.	Knowledge Topic Statement	BT Level	BT Cognitive Demand	BT Verb
FAQ	BPA	142	Methods and techniques to preserve data in an appropriate medium from the INTERNET, and the advantages and disadvantages of each method.	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate
FAQ	BPA	143	Methods and techniques to preserve data remotely from DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS, COMPUTERS and COMPUTER SYSTEMS, via the Internet or other network connection, and the advantages and disadvantages of each method.	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate
FAQ	BPA	144	Methods and techniques to disassemble and reassemble COMPUTERS containing DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS.	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate
FAQ	BPA	145	Methods and techniques to preserve data in an appropriate digital evidence format from DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS, including those that have been removed from COMPUTERS, and the advantages and disadvantages of each method.	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate
FAQ	BPA	146	Methods and techniques to bypass passwords and other authentication methods on DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS, COMPUTERS and COMPUTER SYSTEMS, and the advantages and disadvantages of each method.	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate

Digital Forensic Technician (DFT)

Responsible for the collection and preservation of data containing potential digital evidence, and the identification and extraction of potentially relevant digital evidence from that data, in a forensically sound and legal manner.

DFT Computer Science and Engineering (70 topics)

Foundational knowledge of computing hardware, storage, file systems, operating systems, databases, programming, cryptography, networking, and related technologies.

KA	Sub	No.	Knowledge Topic Statement	BT Level	BT Cognitive Demand	BT Verb
CSE	NLE	001	Numbering systems, including binary, decimal and hexadecimal (including notation, addition, conversions between systems, and signed and unsigned integers).	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
CSE	NLE	002	Bits, nibbles, and bytes, words, DWORDs, and QWORDs in computing systems.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
CSE	NLE	003	Binary logic and Boolean logic.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
CSE	NLE	004	Data encoding systems, including ASCII, Unicode and Base64 (including decoding).	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
CSE	NLE	005	Big endian and little endian.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
CSE	NLE	006	Electrical circuits (Ohm's law, Kirchoff's voltage law, circuit diagrams), digital circuits (transistors, logic gates, integrated circuits), counting using digital circuits (half-adders, full adders, 4bit adders, signed and unsigned numbers), and memory and clock signals (JK Flip-Flops, T FlipFlops).	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
CSE	NLE	007	The purpose and function of computer hardware, including motherboards, processors, RAM, storage devices, GPUs, input devices, output devices, heat sinks, cooling systems, and power supplies.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
CSE	COH	008	CPUs, the components of a CPU (Instruction Set Architecture, Control Unit, Arithmetic Logic Unit, Registers, Clock, Cores, and Cache), the fetchdecode-execute cycle.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
CSE	COH	009	Main Memory, RAM, the stack, the heap, instructions vs. data, execution, debugging, memory cache on secondary storage devices.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
CSE	COH	010	Input/output mechanisms and devices (Peripherals, Network Interface Cards, Data Storage, etc).	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
CSE	COH	011	Bus communication mechanisms.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply

KA	Sub	No.	Knowledge Topic Statement	BT Level	BT Cognitive Demand	BT Verb
CSE	STH	012	The structure and function of physical storage devices (electromechanical magnetic drives, optical drives, magnetic tape, flash storage, and solidstate drives), storage arrays such as RAID, drive controllers, common problems and failures with physical storage devices.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
CSE	STH	013	Data storage structures on physical storage devices (sectors).	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
CSE	STH	014	The purpose of partitions on storage media, partition types (primary and extended), partition data structures (individual structures and system areas in various common partition schemes used by computers, mobile devices, embedded systems, and operational technology).	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
CSE	STH	015	The difference between physical disks and logical volumes.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
CSE	STH	016	Data structures of partition tables, Master Boot Records, and GUID Partition Tables (GPT).	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
CSE	STH	017	The purpose and function of storage media formatting.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
CSE	BPR	018	The purpose and function of BIOS and UEFI, boot order, POST, secure boot.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
CSE	BPR	019	The purpose and function of a Volume Boot Record (VBR), and the data structure of a VBR.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
CSE	FIS	020	The purpose of file systems, and the structure of common file systems (such as FAT, FAT32, exFAT, NTFS, EXT3, EXT4, HFS, HFS+, APFS and AFS) and their individual file system elements (and the types of data stored in each).	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
CSE	FIS	021	The purpose and function of partitions/volumes in files systems.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
CSE	FIS	022	File system metadata structures that keep track of files and directories and changes to these structures, as well as the data structures of each of these structures, including MACB times of files and folders.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
CSE	FIS	023	Logical data storage structures (clusters), and the meaning of allocated and unallocated clusters.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
CSE	FIS	024	Changes to file system data structures when a file or folder is saved onto the volume, or when a file or folder is deleted from the volume, and what happens at both a sector and cluster level.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
CSE	FIS	025	Partition slack, volume slack, file slack, and RAM slack.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
CSE	FIS	026	The purpose and function of journaling systems within a file system, the types of journals, and the data structures of these journals.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
CSE	FIS	027	The purpose and functions of an operating system, including the kernel, processes, hardware and software interrupts, boot loaders, and BIOS.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply

KA	Sub	No.	Knowledge Topic Statement	BT Level	BT Cognitive Demand	BT Verb
CSE	FIS	028	The differences between laptop and desktop operating systems, server operating systems, mobile device operating systems, operational technology (OT) operating systems, and embedded device operating systems.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
CSE	FIS	029	The purpose and function of an operating systems folder structure, the types of files that compose the operating system and their function and purpose.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
CSE	OSA	030	The purpose and function of logging on a COMPUTER or COMPUTER SYSTEM, the different types of log file formats, and the data structures of these formats.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
CSE	OSA	031	The purpose and function of user group, user and system accounts, file and folder permissions and the types thereof, and file and folder flags.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
CSE	OSA	032	The purpose and function of environmental variables within an operating system.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
CSE	OSA	033	The purpose and function of pipes and piping in an operating system.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
CSE	OSA	034	The purpose and function of files and folders, and types of files and folders, including the data structures of these (including file headers, file footers, and other internal data structures such as file metadata).	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
CSE	OSA	035	The purpose and function of unique identifiers in relation to objects within an operating system.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
CSE	OSA	036	The purpose and function of backup systems and types and formats, including full backups, incremental backups, and the data structures thereof.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
CSE	OSA	037	The concept of file fragmentation, how file fragmentation is tracked, and operating system mechanisms that manage file fragmentation.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
CSE	OSA	038	The purpose and function of servers (including web servers, DNS servers, DHCP servers, log servers, print servers, proxy servers, and database servers).	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
CSE	DBS	039	The purpose and function of databases (including the difference between relational and nonrelational databases, tables, SQL commands and statements, SQL operators, database design, data types, database administration, etc.).	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
CSE	DBS	040	The data structures of typical relational and nonrelational databases.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
CSE	OSA	041	Programming concepts including program logic, printing, variables, manipulating strings, manipulating numbers, type conversions, lists and tuples, dictionaries, code comments, conditionals, for loops, while loops, functions, sockets and threads, user inputs, classes and objects, exceptions, arrays, debugging, pointers and memory, the difference between procedural and object-oriented programming, etc.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
CSE	OSA	042	The purpose and function of machine code and assembly language, and assembly language instructions.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
CSE	OSA	043	The purpose and function of high-level programming languages, and typical functions of high-level languages.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply

KA	Sub	No.	Knowledge Topic Statement	BT Level	BT Cognitive Demand	BT Verb
CSE	OSA	044	The purpose and function of cryptography (plaintext and ciphertext, encryption and decryption, algorithms and cryptanalysis, key and keyspace, keyspace and brute force, work factor, encryption systems).	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
CSE	CRS	045	Encryption methods (encryption vs. encoding, symmetric encryption, asymmetric encryption, hashing).	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
CSE	CRS	046	The purpose and function of steganography.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
CSE	CRS	047	The purpose and function of hashing, one way hash algorithms, and hash collisions.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
CSE	CRS	048	The purpose and function of authentication mechanisms (passwords, tokens, biometrics, two-factor authentication, dual-factor authentication, multifactor authentication).	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
CSE	CRS	049	The purpose and function of digital signatures, digital certificates, Public Key Infrastructure (PKI), and the data structures thereof.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
CSE	CRS	050	The purpose and function of virtual private networking.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
CSE	CRS	051	The purpose and function of firewalls, intrusion detection systems, and intrusion prevention systems.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
CSE	NET	052	The purpose and function of the OSI and TCP/IP model.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
CSE	NET	053	The purpose and function of networks (including network topologies, switches, hubs, routers, network interface cards, MAC addresses, IP addresses, data packets, packet headers, protocols and ports, IP4, IP6, network address translation, subnets).	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
CSE	NET	054	The purpose and function of network communication protocols, and the data structures of the data packets used by them (e.g., TCP, UDP, HTTP, FTP, ICMP, DHCP, ARP, HTTPS, TLS, DNSSEC).	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
CSE	NET	055	The purpose and function of wired network connectivity, and the mechanisms used to enable connectivity.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
CSE	NET	056	The purpose and function of wireless network connectivity, the mechanisms to enable connectivity (Wi-Fi and mobile telecommunication such as GSM and 5G+, Bluetooth, Zigbee, NFC, RFID, etc.), and the technology and protocols that enable the connectivity.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
CSE	INT	057	The nature and structure of the Internet.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
CSE	INT	222	The purpose and function of the DNS system (including domain names, top level domains, authoritative name servers, DNS caching, forward and reverse lookups, recursive and iterative lookups, and DNS records).	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
CSE	INT	058	The structure of the World Wide Web, the purpose and function of web servers (including HTTP, HTML, Javascript, PHP, and cookies).	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
CSE	INT	059	The purpose and function of Internet browsers, files associated with Internet browsers, and the data structures of these files.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply

KA	Sub	No.	Knowledge Topic Statement	BT Level	BT Cognitive Demand	BT Verb
CSE	INT	060	The purpose and function of Internet search engines (including search methodologies and techniques).	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
CSE	EMC	061	The purpose and function of email (including email servers, SMTP, POP3, IMAP, MIME, email spoofing, SPF, DKIM, and DMARC).	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
CSE	EMC	062	The data structures of email.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
CSE	EMC	063	The purpose and function of messaging services, and the data structures thereof.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
CSE	EMC	064	The purpose and function of video and audio communication services, and the data structures thereof.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
CSE	VIC	065	The purpose and function of virtualisation (including the role of the hypervisor and the differences between Type 1 and Type 2 hypervisors).	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
CSE	VIC	066	Virtual machine files, file format, and data structures of those files.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
CSE	VIC	067	The purpose and function of cloud computing, including classes of cloud services (IaaS, PaaS, SaaS).	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
CSE	VIC	068	The data structures used by cloud storage (file storage, block storage, object storage).	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
CSE	VIC	069	The purpose and function of containers, and the data structures thereof.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply

DFT Applied Law (12 topics)

Legal knowledge applicable to digital forensics practice, including substantive law, procedural law, the law of evidence, international law, and testifying as an expert witness.

KA	Sub	No.	Knowledge Topic Statement	BT Level	BT Cognitive Demand	BT Verb
APL	SBL	070	Cybercrime laws (jurisdiction dependent).	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
APL	SBL	071	Data privacy laws (jurisdiction dependent).	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
APL	SBL	072	Data interception laws (jurisdiction dependent).	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
APL	SBL	073	Data retention laws (jurisdiction dependent).	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
APL	SBL	074	Regulatory requirements for the practice of digital forensics (jurisdiction dependent).	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate

KA	Sub	No.	Knowledge Topic Statement	BT Level	BT Cognitive Demand	BT Verb
APL	SBL	075	Criminal procedure law relating to the securing, preservation, and use of digital evidence (jurisdiction dependent).	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate
APL	SBL	076	Civil procedure law relating to the securing, preservation, and use of digital evidence (jurisdiction dependent).	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate
APL	LAE	077	The law of evidence in relation to types of evidence; admissibility and relevance of evidence; evidence integrity, the best evidence rules; and exculpatory and inculpatory evidence (jurisdiction dependent).	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate
APL	LAE	078	Legal privilege.	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate
APL	LAE	079	International law relating to digital evidence and cybercrime, including how to legally obtain evidence in other jurisdictions.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
APL	TES	080	Testifying in court as a witness or expert witness, including techniques and methods to present digital evidence and the findings from digital forensics effectively, and methods and techniques to be an effective witness.	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate
APL	TES	081	The obligations of an expert witness.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply

DFT Forensic Science (30 topics)

Forensic principles, scientific reasoning, ethics, minimising bias, documentation, communication, quality assurance, validation, and criminology.

KA	Sub	No.	Knowledge Topic Statement	BT Level	BT Cognitive Demand	BT Verb
FSC	FPR	082	The purpose and function of forensic science as a scientific field: activity and presence produce traces that are vectors of information; scene investigation is a scientific and diagnostic endeavour requiring scientific expertise; forensic science is case-based and reliant on scientific knowledge, investigative methodology and logical reasoning; forensic science is an assessment of findings in context due to time asymmetry; forensic science deals with a continuum of uncertainties; forensic science has multi-dimensional purposes and contributions; forensic science findings acquire meaning in context.	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate
FSC	FPR	083	The purpose and function of digital forensics (the definition of digital forensics, the digital forensics process in terms of ISO 27043).	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate
FSC	FPR	084	Identification of the scope, purpose and objectives of an investigation; the ongoing review of these as the investigation progresses; and the identification of further investigative opportunities.	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate
FSC	FPR	085	The identification of appropriate sources of information and evidence to advance an investigation.	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate
FSC	FPR	086	The fragility of digital evidence.	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate
FSC	FPR	087	The purpose and function of a trace.	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate

KA	Sub	No.	Knowledge Topic Statement	BT Level	BT Cognitive Demand	BT Verb
FSC	FPR	088	The purpose, function and applicability of the Locard Principle.	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate
FSC	SCR	091	The scientific method.	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate
FSC	SCR	092	The purpose and function of a hypothesis, and methods and techniques to develop and test hypotheses.	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate
FSC	SCR	093	The importance of abductive reasoning, and abductive reasoning methods and techniques.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
FSC	SCR	094	The importance of deductive reasoning, and deductive reasoning methods and techniques.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
FSC	SCR	095	The importance of inductive reasoning, and inductive reasoning methods and techniques.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
FSC	SCR	096	The Cognitive Task Model (Bottom-Up Processes, Top-Down Processes, the Foraging Loop, the Sense-Making Loop, Data Extraction vs. Analysis vs. Legal Interpretation).	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate
FSC	ETH	097	The principles of ethical conduct for forensic work, including avoiding conflict of interest, objectivity, and impartiality.	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate
FSC	ETH	098	Principles of ethics applicable to digital forensics.	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate
FSC	ETH	099	Remaining within the levels of one's competency and knowledge.	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate
FSC	MBI	100	The importance of objectivity, and methods and techniques to maintain objectivity.	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate
FSC	MBI	101	The importance of minimising bias, and methods and techniques to identify and counter potential bias.	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate
FSC	MBI	102	The purpose and format of contemporaneous notes during the entire forensic process (from scene to court), including documenting all decisions, actions, options and the rationale related to all lines of enquiry.	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate
FSC	MBI	103	Writing technical reports and affidavits to document findings. The structural requirements of digital forensic reports and affidavits.	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate
FSC	DOC	104	How to ensure and maintain effective communication in an investigation team, to ensure the optimal digital forensics approach and maximise the digital evidence available, and the analysis thereof. This includes information gathering, classification and dissemination.	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate
FSC	COM	105	Communicating technical and scientific data, including concepts and processes, in an easy-to-understand manner, and understanding the standard terminology used in these communications.	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate
FSC	COM	106	Methods and techniques to be able to effectively interview witnesses and persons of interest.	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate

KA	Sub	No.	Knowledge Topic Statement	BT Level	BT Cognitive Demand	BT Verb
FSC	QUA	107	Methods and techniques to perform quality assurance.	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate
FSC	QUA	108	The purpose and function of ISO17020 and ISO17025.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
FSC	VER	109	The purpose and function of testing, validating and verification of digital forensic tools, processes, and procedures; and the methods and techniques to test, validate and verify these.	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate
FSC	CRI	110	Motivations of cybercriminals.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
FSC	CRI	111	Types and categories of cybercriminals (lone actors, groups, gangs and syndicates, organised crime groups, hacktivist groups, terrorist groups, nation-states).	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
FSC	CRI	112	The overlap between cybercrime and other crimes, and how these other crimes can facilitate cybercrime and vice versa.	3 Apply	Apply	Apply
FSC	CRI	113	The purpose and function of modus operandi.	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate

DFT Search and Seizure (14 topics)

Methods and techniques for identifying, documenting, handling, and preserving digital evidence at scenes, including evidence integrity and chain of custody.

KA	Sub	No.	Knowledge Topic Statement	BT Level	BT Cognitive Demand	BT Verb
SAS	EVI	114	Physical scene search techniques and methods.	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate
SAS	EVI	115	The identification of types of COMPUTERS, DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS, or COMPUTER SYSTEMS that contain digital data.	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate
SAS	EVI	116	The identification of other physical evidence at the physical scene that may assist the digital forensics process, such as documents containing potential passwords.	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate
SAS	EVI	117	The types of physical trace evidence that can exist on COMPUTERS, DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS, or COMPUTER SYSTEMS, such as fingerprints or DNA.	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate
SAS	EVI	118	Physical scene documentation techniques, including sketching and mapping, video recording, photography.	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate
SAS	EVI	119	Techniques to document the current state, condition and configuration of any COMPUTERS, DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS, or COMPUTER SYSTEMS to be seized, including photography, videography, uses of labels and photographic scales, and contemporaneous notes.	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate
SAS	EVI	120	Methods to secure physical scenes to ensure the safety of persons at the scene, and prevent damage to or interference with the COMPUTERS, DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS, COMPUTER SYSTEMS, or TRAFFIC DATA at the scene.	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate

KA	Sub	No.	Knowledge Topic Statement	BT Level	BT Cognitive Demand	BT Verb
SAS	EVI	121	Techniques to handle and collect COMPUTERS, DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS, or COMPUTER SYSTEMS in a manner that preserves potential trace evidence such as DNA and fingerprints.	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate
SAS	EIN	122	Techniques used to booby-trap COMPUTERS, DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS, or COMPUTER SYSTEMS, identification techniques and handling of potentially booby-trapped devices.	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate
SAS	EIN	123	Methods to safeguard COMPUTERS, DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS, or COMPUTER SYSTEMS that may contain data, including physical, wireless, and cellular network isolation.	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate
SAS	EIN	124	Methods to preserve power to powered on COMPUTERS, DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS, or COMPUTER SYSTEMS, during seizure and transport, where the device cannot be powered off due to the risk of losing data.	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate
SAS	EIN	125	Methods to correctly and safely power off COMPUTERS, DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS, or COMPUTER SYSTEMS during seizure.	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate
SAS	EIN	126	Techniques to securely package COMPUTERS, DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS, or COMPUTER SYSTEMS to preserve the evidential integrity of the device.	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate
SAS	EIN	127	Techniques to securely transport COMPUTERS, DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS, or COMPUTER SYSTEMS and prevent damage to, or contamination of the COMPUTERS, DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS, or COMPUTER SYSTEMS, or the destruction of trace evidence.	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate

DFT Forensic Acquisition (20 topics)

Methods and techniques for forensically preserving digital data from all categories of computers, data storage media, and computer systems.

KA	Sub	No.	Knowledge Topic Statement	BT Level	BT Cognitive Demand	BT Verb
FAQ	AQS	128	ISO 27037 guidelines for identification, collection, acquisition and preservation of digital evidence.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FAQ	AQS	129	Digital evidence preservation and extraction methods, including physical (every single bit), volume (contents of a volume), file system (all file system data available for extraction), and logical (specific files and directories), and the suitability of each method based on case circumstances, and the advantages and disadvantages of each method.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FAQ	DEF	130	Digital evidence formats used to preserve data from COMPUTERS, DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS, or COMPUTER SYSTEMS, including raw disk images, forensic image files, forensic copies, backups, etc, and the advantages and disadvantages of each.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FAQ	DEF	223	Data structure of common forensic image file formats, such as EWF, AFF, etc.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FAQ	DEF	131	Methods and techniques to sterilise DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS used for storing digital evidence, and how to mathematically verify the sterilisation.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FAQ	EIN	132	Methods and techniques to verify the integrity of preserved digital evidence formats through oneway cryptographic hashing (MD5, SHA1, SHA256, etc.) and thorough documentation.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FAQ	EIN	133	The purpose and function of write blocking for DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique

KA	Sub	No.	Knowledge Topic Statement	BT Level	BT Cognitive Demand	BT Verb
FAQ	EIN	134	Methods and techniques for hardware write blocking for DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS, and the advantages and disadvantages thereof.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FAQ	LAM	135	Methods and techniques for software write blocking for DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS, and the advantages and disadvantages thereof.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FAQ	LAM	136	Order of volatility of data, and the importance of acquiring the most volatile data in the best order on COMPUTERS and COMPUTER SYSTEMS.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FAQ	LAM	137	The impact on COMPUTERS, DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS, or COMPUTER SYSTEMS, including RAM and file system changes, when accessing these while they are powered on, and techniques to minimise this impact.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FAQ	LAM	138	Methods and techniques to preserve a memory image or other volatile data from RAM or other volatile storage on a powered on COMPUTER or COMPUTER SYSTEM, and the advantages and disadvantages of each method.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FAQ	LAM	139	Methods and techniques to identify volume or disk encryption on DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS on a powered on COMPUTER, and the importance of obtaining a logical image of the unencrypted data before powering down the COMPUTER, and the advantages and disadvantages of each method.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FAQ	LAM	140	Methods and techniques to preserve data in an appropriate digital evidence format from DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS on a powered on COMPUTER, and the advantages and disadvantages of each method.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FAQ	LAM	141	Methods and techniques to preserve TRAFFIC DATA in an appropriate digital evidence format from COMPUTER SYSTEMS, and the advantages and disadvantages of each method.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FAQ	LAM	142	Methods and techniques to preserve data in an appropriate medium from the INTERNET, and the advantages and disadvantages of each method.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FAQ	BPA	143	Methods and techniques to preserve data remotely from DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS, COMPUTERS and COMPUTER SYSTEMS, via the Internet or other network connection, and the advantages and disadvantages of each method.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FAQ	BPA	144	Methods and techniques to disassemble and reassemble COMPUTERS containing DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FAQ	BPA	145	Methods and techniques to preserve data in an appropriate digital evidence format from DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS, including those that have been removed from COMPUTERS, and the advantages and disadvantages of each method.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FAQ	BPA	146	Methods and techniques to bypass passwords and other authentication methods on DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS, COMPUTERS and COMPUTER SYSTEMS, and the advantages and disadvantages of each method.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique

DFT Forensic Examination (63 topics)

Methods and techniques for identifying and extracting potentially relevant digital evidence from forensically acquired data.

KA	Sub	No.	Knowledge Topic Statement	BT Level	BT Cognitive Demand	BT Verb
FEX	INV	147	The advantages and disadvantages of specific forensics software applications, and the importance of knowing the capacity and ability of any digital forensic software application used.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FEX	INV	148	The identification of data that is potentially relevant or related to the investigation being conducted.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FEX	EXS	150	ISO 27041 Guidance on Assuring Suitability and Adequacy of Investigative Method.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FEX	EXS	151	ISO 27050 Electronic Discovery.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FEX	TRI	152	Methods and techniques to preview the data on COMPUTERS, DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS, and COMPUTER SYSTEMS from both powered on devices, and forensic images; to identify information of immediate value to advance an investigation.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FEX	DAR	153	The nature of orphan files, and methods to identify and recover orphan files.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FEX	DAR	154	The nature of deleted files and directories, and detected records or data within other files.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FEX	DAR	155	Deleted file and folder recovery techniques using file system metadata records.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FEX	DAR	156	Deleted file and folder recovery techniques using data carving from unallocated clusters.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FEX	DAR	157	Techniques for carving DATA STRUCTURES (not files) from unallocated clusters, or within files.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FEX	DAR	158	Methods and techniques to rebuild files and DATA STRUCTURES from packet captures.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FEX	DAR	160	Methods and techniques to rebuild data streams from captured network data.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FEX	DAR	161	Methods and techniques to build a searchable index of all human-readable string data from a forensic image, including the location of where the data is.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FEX	DAR	162	Methods and techniques to search and identify string data (specific string matching, Boolean terms, fuzzy matching, proximal matching, REGEX, etc.) and identify the folders, files, data structures, or locations in unallocated space where the string data is found.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FEX	DAR	163	Methods and techniques to identify folders, files, and DATA STRUCTURES, and to parse data from these for examination.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique

KA	Sub	No.	Knowledge Topic Statement	BT Level	BT Cognitive Demand	BT Verb
FEX	DSP	164	Methods and techniques to identify file types based on file signatures.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FEX	DSP	165	Methods and techniques to identify and parse file system metadata structures for examination.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FEX	DSP	166	Methods and techniques to identify the format of various date and time stamps, and to decode these into a human-readable format.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FEX	DSP	167	Methods and techniques to extract data from compound files.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FEX	DSP	168	Methods and techniques to search graphic, audio and video files.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FEX	DSP	169	Methods and techniques to identify database file formats, identify the table and format structures within the database, and extract or query the data contained in the database.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FEX	DSP	170	Methods and techniques to examine the contents of a binary file to determine functionality (both static and dynamic methods) and extract other case relevant data.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FEX	DSP	171	Methods and techniques to build a timeline from the data available from a file system forensic image, a memory image, or packet captures.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FEX	DSP	172	Methods and techniques to virtualise a forensic image and enable the booting of the forensic image as if it were an actual COMPUTER so that the COMPUTER can be observed in the same way the user thereof did.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FEX	DSP	173	Methods and techniques to identify internal file metadata and parse it out for examination.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FEX	DSP	174	Methods and techniques to identify encoded and obfuscated data strings, and methods and techniques to decode or deobfuscate the data strings.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FEX	DSP	175	Scripting to parse data from files and data structures.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FEX	DSP	176	Methods and techniques to decrypt encrypted volumes, folders and files.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FEX	DSP	177	Methods and techniques to extract folders, files, and data structures from a memory image.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FEX	DSP	178	Methods and techniques to parse file system structures and to navigate through a file system.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FEX	DSP	179	Methods and techniques to interact with a COMPUTER at a command line level.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FEX	DSP	180	Calculation of hash values from files, file fragments, DATA STRUCTURES within files or unallocated space using one-way hash algorithms (MD5, SHA, etc.).	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique

KA	Sub	No.	Knowledge Topic Statement	BT Level	BT Cognitive Demand	BT Verb
FEX	DSP	181	Using hash data sets of known good, known malicious, and known contraband files, to exclude files, or identify files.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FEX	DSP	182	Obtaining the data available from COMPUTERS in a before first unlock state (BFU) or in an after first unlock state (AFU).	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FEX	IDE	183	Methods and techniques to identify encrypted files, files containing steganography data, alternate data streams, file extensions and type mismatches, and other concealed or hidden data.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FEX	IDE	184	Methods and techniques to identify known malicious and potentially malicious executable files.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FEX	IDE	185	Methods and techniques to identify the installed operating system, and default files and directory structures used by the identified operating system.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FEX	IDE	186	Methods and techniques to determine baseline normal activity within a COMPUTER or COMPUTER SYSTEM and contrast that to current activity within a COMPUTER or COMPUTER SYSTEM, to determine potentially abnormal activity.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FEX	IDE	187	Files and data structures that can identify that a user has used cloud storage services (accessed files, uploaded files, downloaded files, shared files, edited files, deleted files).	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FEX	IDE	188	Files and data structures that can identify that a user has used email (composed email, read email, sent email, set email rules, etc.).	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FEX	IDE	189	Files and data structures that can identify that an application had been executed, and where relevant, which account executed it.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FEX	IDE	190	Files and data structures that can identify the existence of a file or folder that is no longer present within the file system.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FEX	IDE	191	Files and data structures that can identify that a file or folder had been deleted by an account.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FEX	IDE	192	Files and folders that are typically installed and used by an operating system.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FEX	IDE	193	Files and data structures that can identify system configurations.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FEX	IDE	194	Files and data structures that can identify user preferences.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FEX	IDE	195	Files and data structures that can identify program installation.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FEX	IDE	196	Files and data structures that can identify Internet and other online activities by an account.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FEX	IDE	197	Files and data structures that can identify files that have been downloaded by an account.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique

KA	Sub	No.	Knowledge Topic Statement	BT Level	BT Cognitive Demand	BT Verb
FEX	IDE	198	Files and data structures that can identify account usage.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FEX	IDE	199	Files and data structures that can show network activity and communications between COMPUTERS.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FEX	IDE	200	Files and data structures that can identify timezone settings, and dates and file system timestamps of files and folders, and what caused these timestamps to be written or updated.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FEX	IDE	201	Files and data structures that can identify the actual or approximate physical location of a COMPUTER at a particular point in time.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FEX	IDE	202	Files and data structures that can identify external devices connected to the COMPUTER, when they were used, and what was accessed or transferred to them.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FEX	IDE	203	Files and data structures that can identify system events.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FEX	IDE	204	Files and data structures that can identify electronic communications between parties (email, internet chats, chat apps, video chats, phone calls, SMS, etc.).	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FEX	IDE	205	Files and data structures that can identify files moved between COMPUTERS via a network.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FEX	IDE	206	Files and data structures that can identify remote access between COMPUTERS via a network.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FEX	IDE	207	Files and data structures that can identify remote execution between COMPUTERS via a network.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FEX	IDE	208	Files and data structures that can identify synchronisation between COMPUTERS and online data sources, what was synchronised and when, and what COMPUTERS have been paired to each other.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FEX	IDE	209	Files and data structures that can be used to identify time manipulation, data structures manipulation, data destruction, and data hiding.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FEX	IDE	224	Files and data structures that can identify the existence of an executable file that is no longer present within the file system.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FEX	IDE	225	Files and data structures that can identify that a file or folder had been accessed by an account.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique

DFT Forensic Analysis (12 topics)

Methods and techniques for the analysis, reconstruction, interpretation, and evaluation of digital evidence to answer forensic questions.

KA	Sub	No.	Knowledge Topic Statement	BT Level	BT Cognitive Demand	BT Verb
FAN	FAS	210	ISO 27042 Guidelines for the Analysis and Interpretation of Digital Evidence.	1 Remember	Remember	Define
FAN	SCM	211	Methods and techniques to develop and test hypotheses using the scientific method.	1 Remember	Remember	Define
FAN	SCM	212	Methods and techniques to conduct scientifically valid experimentation.	1 Remember	Remember	Define
FAN	SCM	213	Methods and techniques to calculate and determine statistical validity and probability.	1 Remember	Remember	Define
FAN	SCM	214	Methods and techniques to establish a level of confidence in the authenticity of any particular trace (including integrity and providence of the trace, contextual descriptions, and temporal restrictions).	1 Remember	Remember	Define
FAN	SCM	215	Methods and techniques to establish sufficient confidence that some identity-related information describes a specific entity or object in a given context, at a certain time.	2 Understand	Understand	Explain
FAN	SCM	216	Methods and techniques to develop taxonomies of traces and the decision process attempting to ascribe a trace with sufficient confidence to its class on the basis of characteristics that are common among traces of the same class, distinguishing them from traces of other classes.	1 Remember	Remember	Define
FAN	EVM	217	Methods and techniques to organise observed traces to disclose the most likely operational conditions or capabilities (functional analysis), patterns in time (temporal analysis), and linkages between entities – people, places, objects (relational analysis).	1 Remember	Remember	Define
FAN	EVM	218	Methods and techniques to evaluate the evidence, to allow a decision process to be taken in relation to that evidence.	1 Remember	Remember	Define
FAN	RAA	219	Reconstruction of past activity.	1 Remember	Remember	Define
FAN	RAA	220	Methods and techniques to attribute activities on a COMPUTER or COMPUTER SYSTEM to an actual person.	2 Understand	Understand	Explain
FAN	RAA	221	Methods and techniques to determine intention.	1 Remember	Remember	Define

Digital Forensic Scientist (DFS)

Responsible for the collection and preservation of data containing potential digital evidence, the identification and extraction of potentially relevant digital evidence, and the analysis and interpretation of the digital evidence. May also testify as an expert witness in court.

DFS Computer Science and Engineering (70 topics)

Foundational knowledge of computing hardware, storage, file systems, operating systems, databases, programming, cryptography, networking, and related technologies.

KA	Sub	No.	Knowledge Topic Statement	BT Level	BT Cognitive Demand	BT Verb
CSE	NLE	001	Numbering systems, including binary, decimal and hexadecimal (including notation, addition, conversions between systems, and signed and unsigned integers).	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
CSE	NLE	002	Bits, nibbles, and bytes, words, DWORDs, and QWORDs in computing systems.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
CSE	NLE	003	Binary logic and Boolean logic.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
CSE	NLE	004	Data encoding systems, including ASCII, Unicode and Base64 (including decoding).	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
CSE	NLE	005	Big endian and little endian.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
CSE	NLE	006	Electrical circuits (Ohm's law, Kirchoff's voltage law, circuit diagrams), digital circuits (transistors, logic gates, integrated circuits), counting using digital circuits (half-adders, full adders, 4bit adders, signed and unsigned numbers), and memory and clock signals (JK Flip-Flops, T FlipFlops).	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
CSE	NLE	007	The purpose and function of computer hardware, including motherboards, processors, RAM, storage devices, GPUs, input devices, output devices, heat sinks, cooling systems, and power supplies.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
CSE	NLE	008	CPUs, the components of a CPU (Instruction Set Architecture, Control Unit, Arithmetic Logic Unit, Registers, Clock, Cores, and Cache), the fetchdecode-execute cycle.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
CSE	COH	009	Main Memory, RAM, the stack, the heap, instructions vs. data, execution, debugging, memory cache on secondary storage devices.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
CSE	COH	010	Input/output mechanisms and devices (Peripherals, Network Interface Cards, Data Storage, etc).	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
CSE	COH	011	Bus communication mechanisms.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique

KA	Sub	No.	Knowledge Topic Statement	BT Level	BT Cognitive Demand	BT Verb
CSE	STH	012	The structure and function of physical storage devices (electromechanical magnetic drives, optical drives, magnetic tape, flash storage, and solidstate drives), storage arrays such as RAID, drive controllers, common problems and failures with physical storage devices.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
CSE	STH	013	Data storage structures on physical storage devices (sectors).	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
CSE	STH	014	The purpose of partitions on storage media, partition types (primary and extended), partition data structures (individuals structures and systems areas in various common partition schemes used by computers, mobile devices, embedded systems, and operational technology).	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
CSE	STH	015	The difference between physical disks and logical volumes.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
CSE	STH	016	Data structures of partition tables, Master Boot Records, and GUID Partition Tables (GPT).	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
CSE	STH	017	The purpose and function of storage media formatting.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
CSE	BPR	018	The purpose and function of BIOS and UEFI, boot order, POST, secure boot.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
CSE	BPR	019	The purpose and function of a Volume Boot Record (VBR), and the data structure of a VBR.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
CSE	FIS	020	The purpose of file systems, and the structure of common file systems (such as FAT, FAT32, exFAT, NTFS, EXT3, EXT4, HFS, HFS+, APFS and AFS) and their individual file system elements (and the types of data stored in each).	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
CSE	FIS	021	The purpose and function of partitions/volumes in files systems.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
CSE	FIS	022	File system metadata structures that keep track of files and directories and changes to these structures, as well as the data structures of each of these structures, including MACB times of files and folders.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
CSE	FIS	023	Logical data storage structures (clusters), and the meaning of allocated and unallocated clusters.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
CSE	FIS	024	Changes to file system data structures when a file or folder is saved onto the volume, or when a file or folder is deleted from the volume, and what happens at both a sector and cluster level.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
CSE	FIS	025	Partition slack, volume slack, file slack, and RAM slack.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
CSE	FIS	026	The purpose and function of journaling systems within a file system, the types of journals, and the data structures of these journals.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
CSE	FIS	027	The purpose and functions of an operating system, including the kernel, processes, hardware and software interrupts, boot loaders, and BIOS.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique

KA	Sub	No.	Knowledge Topic Statement	BT Level	BT Cognitive Demand	BT Verb
CSE	FIS	028	The differences between laptop and desktop operating systems, server operating systems, mobile device operating systems, operational technology (OT) operating systems, and embedded device operating systems.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
CSE	FIS	029	The purpose and function of an operating systems folder structure, the types of files that compose the operating system and their function and purpose.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
CSE	OSA	030	The purpose and function of logging on a COMPUTER or COMPUTER SYSTEM, the different types of log file formats, and the data structures of these formats.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
CSE	OSA	031	The purpose and function of user group, user and system accounts, file and folder permissions and the types thereof, and file and folder flags.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
CSE	OSA	032	The purpose and function of environmental variables within an operating system.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
CSE	OSA	033	The purpose and function of pipes and piping in an operating system.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
CSE	OSA	034	The purpose and function of files and folders, and types of files and folders, including the data structures of these (including file headers, file footers, and other internal data structures such as file metadata).	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
CSE	OSA	035	The purpose and function of unique identifiers in relation to objects within an operating system.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
CSE	OSA	036	The purpose and function of backup systems and types and formats, including full backups, incremental backups, and the data structures thereof.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
CSE	OSA	037	The concept of file fragmentation, how file fragmentation is tracked, and operating system mechanisms that manage file fragmentation.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
CSE	OSA	038	The purpose and function of servers (including web servers, DNS servers, DHCP servers, log servers, print servers, proxy servers, and database servers).	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
CSE	DBS	039	The purpose and function of databases (including the difference between relational and nonrelational databases, tables, SQL commands and statements, SQL operators, database design, data types, database administration, etc.).	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
CSE	DBS	040	The data structures of typical relational and nonrelational databases.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
CSE	OSA	041	Programming concepts including program logic, printing, variables, manipulating strings, manipulating numbers, type conversions, lists and tuples, dictionaries, code comments, conditionals, for loops, while loops, functions, sockets and threads, user inputs, classes and objects, exceptions, arrays, debugging, pointers and memory, the difference between procedural and object-oriented programming, etc.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
CSE	OSA	042	The purpose and function of machine code and assembly language, and assembly language instructions.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
CSE	OSA	043	The purpose and function of high-level programming languages, and typical functions of high-level languages.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique

KA	Sub	No.	Knowledge Topic Statement	BT Level	BT Cognitive Demand	BT Verb
CSE	OSA	044	The purpose and function of cryptography (plaintext and ciphertext, encryption and decryption, algorithms and cryptanalysis, key and keyspace, keyspace and bruteforce, work factor, encryption systems).	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
CSE	CRS	045	Encryption methods (encryption vs. encoding, symmetric encryption, asymmetric encryption, hashing).	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
CSE	CRS	046	The purpose and function of stenography.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
CSE	CRS	047	The purpose and function of hashing, one way hash algorithms, and hash collisions.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
CSE	CRS	048	The purpose and function of authentication mechanisms (passwords, tokens, biometrics, two-factor authentication, dual-factor authentication, multifactor authentication).	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
CSE	CRS	049	The purpose and function of digital signatures, digital certificates, Public Key Infrastructure (PKI), and the data structures thereof.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
CSE	CRS	050	The purpose and function of virtual private networking.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
CSE	CRS	051	The purpose and function of firewalls, intrusion detection systems, and intrusion prevention systems.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
CSE	NET	052	The purpose and function of the OSI and TCP/IP model.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
CSE	NET	053	The purpose and function of networks (including network topologies, switches, hubs, routers, network interface cards, MAC addresses, IP addresses, data packets, packet headers, protocols and ports, IP4, IP6, network address translation, subnets).	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
CSE	NET	054	The purpose and function of network communication protocols, and the data structures of the data packets used by them (e.g., TCP, UDP, HTTP, FTP, ICMP, DHCP, ARP, HTTPS, TLS, DNSSEC).	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
CSE	NET	055	The purpose and function of wired network connectivity, and the mechanisms used to enable connectivity.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
CSE	NET	056	The purpose and function of wireless network connectivity, the mechanisms to enable connectivity (Wi-Fi and mobile telecommunication such as GSM and 5G+, Bluetooth, Zigbee, NFC, RFID, etc.), and the technology and protocols that enable the connectivity.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
CSE	INT	057	The nature and structure of the Internet.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
CSE	INT	222	The purpose and function of the DNS system (including domain names, top level domains, authoritative name servers, DNS caching, forward and reverse lookups, recursive and iterative lookups, and DNS records).	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
CSE	INT	058	The structure of the World Wide Web, the purpose and function of web servers (including HTTP, HTML, Javascript, PHP, and cookies).	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
CSE	INT	059	The purpose and function of Internet browsers, files associated with Internet browsers, and the data structures of these files.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique

KA	Sub	No.	Knowledge Topic Statement	BT Level	BT Cognitive Demand	BT Verb
CSE	INT	060	The purpose and function of Internet search engines (including search methodologies and techniques).	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
CSE	EMC	061	The purpose and function of email (including email servers, SMTP, POP3, IMAP, MIME, email spoofing, SPF, DKIM, and DMARC).	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
CSE	EMC	062	The data structures of email.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
CSE	EMC	063	The purpose and function of messaging services, and the data structures thereof.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
CSE	EMC	064	The purpose and function of video and audio communication services, and the data structures thereof.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
CSE	VIC	065	The purpose and function of virtualisation (including the role of the hypervisor and the differences between Type 1 and Type 2 hypervisors).	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
CSE	VIC	066	Virtual machine files, file format, and data structures of those files.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
CSE	VIC	067	The purpose and function of cloud computing, including classes of cloud services (IaaS, PaaS, SaaS).	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
CSE	VIC	068	The data structures used by cloud storage (file storage, block storage, object storage).	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
CSE	VIC	069	The purpose and function of containers, and the data structures thereof.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique

DFS Applied Law (12 topics)

Legal knowledge applicable to digital forensics practice, including substantive law, procedural law, the law of evidence, international law, and testifying as an expert witness.

KA	Sub	No.	Knowledge Topic Statement	BT Level	BT Cognitive Demand	BT Verb
APL	SBL	070	Cybercrime laws (jurisdiction dependent).	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
APL	SBL	071	Data privacy laws (jurisdiction dependent).	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
APL	SBL	072	Data interception laws (jurisdiction dependent).	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
APL	SBL	073	Data retention laws (jurisdiction dependent).	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
APL	SBL	074	Regulatory requirements for the practice of digital forensics (jurisdiction dependent).	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique

KA	Sub	No.	Knowledge Topic Statement	BT Level	BT Cognitive Demand	BT Verb
APL	SBL	075	Criminal procedure law relating to the securing, preservation, and use of digital evidence (jurisdiction dependent).	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
APL	SBL	076	Civil procedure law relating to the securing, preservation, and use of digital evidence (jurisdiction dependent).	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
APL	LAE	077	The law of evidence in relation to types of evidence; admissibility and relevance of evidence; evidence integrity, the best evidence rules; and exculpatory and inculpatory evidence (jurisdiction dependent).	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
APL	LAE	078	Legal privilege.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
APL	LAE	079	International law relating to digital evidence and cybercrime, including how to legally obtain evidence in other jurisdictions.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
APL	TES	080	Testifying in court as a witness or expert witness, including techniques and methods to present digital evidence and the findings from digital forensics effectively and methods and techniques to be an effective witness.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
APL	TES	081	The obligations of an expert witness.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise

DFS Forensic Science (30 topics)

Forensic principles, scientific reasoning, ethics, minimising bias, documentation, communication, quality assurance, validation, and criminology.

KA	Sub	No.	Knowledge Topic Statement	BT Level	BT Cognitive Demand	BT Verb
FSC	FPR	082	The purpose and function of forensic science as a scientific field: activity and presence produce traces that are vectors of information; scene investigation is a scientific and diagnostic endeavour requiring scientific expertise; forensic science is case-based and reliant on scientific knowledge, investigative methodology and logical reasoning; forensic science is an assessment of findings in context due to time asymmetry; forensic science deals with a continuum of uncertainties; forensic science has multi-dimensional purposes and contributions; forensic science findings acquire meaning in context.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FSC	FPR	083	The purpose and function of digital forensics (the definition of digital forensics, the digital forensics process in terms of ISO 27043).	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FSC	FPR	084	Identification of the scope, purpose and objectives of an investigation; the ongoing review of these as the investigation progresses; and the identification of further investigative opportunities.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FSC	FPR	085	The identification of appropriate sources of information and evidence to advance an investigation.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FSC	FPR	086	The fragility of digital evidence.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FSC	FPR	087	The purpose and function of a trace.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique

KA	Sub	No.	Knowledge Topic Statement	BT Level	BT Cognitive Demand	BT Verb
FSC	FPR	088	The purpose, function and applicability of the Locard Principle.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FSC	SCR	091	The scientific method.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FSC	SCR	092	The purpose and function of a hypothesis, and methods and techniques to develop and test hypotheses.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FSC	SCR	093	The importance of abductive reasoning, and abductive reasoning methods and techniques.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FSC	SCR	094	The importance of deductive reasoning, and deductive reasoning methods and techniques.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FSC	SCR	095	The importance of inductive reasoning, and inductive reasoning methods and techniques.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FSC	SCR	096	The Cognitive Task Model (Bottom-Up Processes, Top-Down Processes, the Foraging Loop, the Sense-Making Loop, Data Extraction vs. Analysis vs. Legal Interpretation).	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FSC	ETH	097	The principles of ethical conduct for forensic work, including avoiding conflict of interest, objectivity, and impartiality.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FSC	ETH	098	Principles of ethics applicable to digital forensics.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FSC	ETH	099	Remaining within the levels of one's competency and knowledge.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FSC	MBI	100	The importance of objectivity, and methods and techniques to maintain objectivity.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FSC	MBI	101	The importance of minimising bias, and methods and techniques to identify and counter potential bias.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FSC	MBI	102	The purpose and format of contemporaneous notes during the entire forensic process (from scene to court), including documenting all decisions, actions, options and the rationale related to all lines of enquiry.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FSC	MBI	103	Writing technical reports and affidavits to document findings. The structural requirements of digital forensic reports and affidavits.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FSC	DOC	104	How to ensure and maintain effective communication in an investigation team, to ensure the optimal digital forensics approach and maximise the available digital evidence available, and the analysis thereof. This includes information gathering, classification and dissemination.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique
FSC	COM	105	Communicating technical and scientific data, including concepts and processes, in an easy-to-understand manner, and understanding the standard terminology used in these communications.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FSC	COM	106	Methods and techniques to be able to interview witnesses and persons of interest effectively.	5 Evaluate	Evaluate	Critique

KA	Sub	No.	Knowledge Topic Statement	BT Level	BT Cognitive Demand	BT Verb
FSC	QUA	107	Methods and techniques to perform quality assurance.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FSC	QUA	108	The purpose and function of ISO17020 and ISO17025.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FSC	VER	109	The purpose and function of testing, validating and verification of digital forensic tools, processes, and procedures; and the methods and techniques to test, validate and verify these.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FSC	CRI	110	Motivations of cybercriminals.	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate
FSC	CRI	111	Types and categories of cybercriminals (lone actors, groups, gangs and syndicates, organised crime groups, hacktivist groups, terrorist groups, nation-states).	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate
FSC	CRI	112	The overlap between cybercrime and other crimes, and how these other crimes can facilitate cybercrime and vice versa.	4 Analyse	Analyse	Evaluate
FSC	CRI	113	The purpose and function of modus operandi.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise

DFS Search and Seizure (14 topics)

Methods and techniques for identifying, documenting, handling, and preserving digital evidence at scenes, including evidence integrity and chain of custody.

KA	Sub	No.	Knowledge Topic Statement	BT Level	BT Cognitive Demand	BT Verb
SAS	EVI	114	Physical scene search techniques and methods.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
SAS	EVI	115	The identification of types of COMPUTERS, DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS, or COMPUTER SYSTEMS that contain digital data.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
SAS	EVI	116	The identification of other physical evidence at the physical scene that may assist the digital forensics process, such as documents containing potential passwords.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
SAS	EVI	117	The types of physical trace evidence that can exist on COMPUTERS, DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS, or COMPUTER SYSTEMS, such as fingerprints or DNA.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
SAS	EVI	118	Physical scene documentation techniques, including sketching and mapping, video recording, photography.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
SAS	EVI	119	Techniques to document the current state, condition and configuration of any COMPUTERS, DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS, or COMPUTER SYSTEMS to be seized, including photography, videography, uses of labels and photographic scales, and contemporaneous notes.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
SAS	EVI	120	Methods to secure physical scenes to ensure the safety of persons at the scene, and prevent damage to or interference with the COMPUTERS, DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS, COMPUTER SYSTEMS, or TRAFFIC DATA at the scene.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise

KA	Sub	No.	Knowledge Topic Statement	BT Level	BT Cognitive Demand	BT Verb
SAS	EVI	121	Techniques to handle and collect COMPUTERS, DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS, or COMPUTER SYSTEMS in a manner that preserves potential trace evidence such as DNA and fingerprints.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
SAS	EIN	122	Techniques used to booby-trap COMPUTERS, DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS, or COMPUTER SYSTEMS, identification techniques and handling of potentially booby-trapped devices.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
SAS	EIN	123	Methods to safeguard COMPUTERS, DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS, or COMPUTER SYSTEMS that may contain data, including physical, wireless, and cellular network isolation.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
SAS	EIN	124	Methods to preserve power to powered on COMPUTERS, DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS, or COMPUTER SYSTEMS, during seizure and transport, where the device cannot be powered off due to the risk of losing data.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
SAS	EIN	125	Methods to correctly and safely power off COMPUTERS, DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS, or COMPUTER SYSTEMS during seizure.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
SAS	EIN	126	Techniques to securely package COMPUTERS, DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS, or COMPUTER SYSTEMS to preserve the evidential integrity of the device.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
SAS	EIN	127	Techniques to securely transport COMPUTERS, DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS, or COMPUTER SYSTEMS and prevent damage to, or contamination of the COMPUTERS, DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS, or COMPUTER SYSTEMS, or the destruction of trace evidence.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise

DFS Forensic Acquisition (20 topics)

Methods and techniques for forensically preserving digital data from all categories of computers, data storage media, and computer systems.

KA	Sub	No.	Knowledge Topic Statement	BT Level	BT Cognitive Demand	BT Verb
FAQ	AQS	128	ISO 27037 guidelines for identification, collection, acquisition and preservation of digital evidence.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FAQ	AQS	129	Digital evidence preservation and extraction methods, including physical (every single bit), volume (contents of a volume), file system (all file system data available for extraction), and logical (specific files and directories), and the suitability of each method based on case circumstances, and the advantages and disadvantages of each method.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FAQ	DEF	130	Digital evidence formats used to preserve data from COMPUTERS, DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS, or COMPUTER SYSTEMS, including raw disk images, forensic image files, forensic copies, backups, etc, and the advantages and disadvantages of each.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FAQ	DEF	223	Data structure of common forensic image file formats, such as EWF, AFF, etc.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FAQ	DEF	131	Methods and techniques to sterilise DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS used for storing digital evidence, and how to mathematically verify the sterilisation.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FAQ	EIN	132	Methods and techniques to verify the integrity of preserved digital evidence formats through oneway cryptographic hashing (MD5, SHA1, SHA256, etc.) and thorough documentation.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FAQ	EIN	133	The purpose and function of write blocking for DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise

KA	Sub	No.	Knowledge Topic Statement	BT Level	BT Cognitive Demand	BT Verb
FAQ	EIN	134	Methods and techniques for hardware write blocking for DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS, and the advantages and disadvantages thereof.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FAQ	LAM	135	Methods and techniques for software write blocking for DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS, and the advantages and disadvantages thereof.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FAQ	LAM	136	Order of volatility of data, and the importance of acquiring the most volatile data in the best order on COMPUTERS and COMPUTER SYSTEMS.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FAQ	LAM	137	The impact on COMPUTERS, DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS, or COMPUTER SYSTEMS, including RAM and file system changes, when accessing these while they are powered on, and techniques to minimise this impact.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FAQ	LAM	138	Methods and techniques to preserve a memory image or other volatile data from RAM or other volatile storage on a powered on COMPUTER or COMPUTER SYSTEM, and the advantages and disadvantages of each method.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FAQ	LAM	139	Methods and techniques to identify volume or disk encryption on DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS on a powered on COMPUTER, and the importance of obtaining a logical image of the unencrypted data before powering down the COMPUTER, and the advantages and disadvantages of each method.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FAQ	LAM	140	Methods and techniques to preserve data in an appropriate digital evidence format from DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS on a powered on COMPUTER, and the advantages and disadvantages of each method.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FAQ	LAM	141	Methods and techniques to preserve TRAFFIC DATA in an appropriate digital evidence format from COMPUTER SYSTEMS, and the advantages and disadvantages of each method.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FAQ	LAM	142	Methods and techniques to preserve data in an appropriate medium from the INTERNET, and the advantages and disadvantages of each method.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FAQ	BPA	143	Methods and techniques to preserve data remotely from DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS, COMPUTERS and COMPUTER SYSTEMS, via the Internet or other network connection, and the advantages and disadvantages of each method.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FAQ	BPA	144	Methods and techniques to disassemble and reassemble COMPUTERS containing DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FAQ	BPA	145	Methods and techniques to preserve data in an appropriate digital evidence format from DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS, including those that have been removed from COMPUTERS, and the advantages and disadvantages of each method.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FAQ	BPA	146	Methods and techniques to bypass passwords and other authentication methods on DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS, COMPUTERS and COMPUTER SYSTEMS, and the advantages and disadvantages of each method.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise

DFS Forensic Examination (63 topics)

Methods and techniques for identifying and extracting potentially relevant digital evidence from forensically acquired data.

KA	Sub	No.	Knowledge Topic Statement	BT Level	BT Cognitive Demand	BT Verb
FEX	INV	147	The advantages and disadvantages of specific forensics software applications, and the importance of knowing the capacity and ability of any digital forensic software application used.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FEX	INV	148	The identification of data that is potentially relevant or related to the investigation being conducted.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FEX	EXS	150	ISO 27041 Guidance on Assuring Suitability and Adequacy of Investigative Method.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FEX	EXS	151	ISO 27050 Electronic Discovery.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FEX	TRI	152	Methods and techniques to preview the data on COMPUTERS, DATA STORAGE MEDIUMS, and COMPUTER SYSTEMS from both powered on devices, and forensic images; to identify information of immediate value to advance an investigation.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FEX	DAR	153	The nature of orphan files, and methods to identify and recover orphan files.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FEX	DAR	154	The nature of deleted files and directories, and detected records or data within other files.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FEX	DAR	155	Deleted file and folder recovery techniques using file system metadata records.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FEX	DAR	156	Deleted file and folder recovery techniques using data carving from unallocated clusters.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FEX	DAR	157	Techniques for carving DATA STRUCTURES (not files) from unallocated clusters, or within files.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FEX	DAR	158	Methods and techniques to rebuild files and DATA STRUCTURES from packet captures.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FEX	DAR	160	Methods and techniques to rebuild data streams from captured network data.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FEX	DAR	161	Methods and techniques to build a searchable index of all human-readable string data from a forensic image, including the location of where the data is.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FEX	DAR	162	Methods and techniques to search and identify string data (specific string matching, Boolean terms, fuzzy matching, proximal matching, REGEX, etc.) and identify the folders, files, data structures, or locations in unallocated space where the string data is found.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FEX	DAR	163	Methods and techniques to identify folders, files, and DATA STRUCTURES, and to parse data from these for examination.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise

KA	Sub	No.	Knowledge Topic Statement	BT Level	BT Cognitive Demand	BT Verb
FEX	DSP	164	Methods and techniques to identify file types based on file signatures.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FEX	DSP	165	Methods and techniques to identify and parse file system metadata structures for examination.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FEX	DSP	166	Methods and techniques to identify the format of various date and time stamps, and to decode these into a human-readable format.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FEX	DSP	167	Methods and techniques to extract data from compound files.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FEX	DSP	168	Methods and techniques to search graphic, audio and video files.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FEX	DSP	169	Methods and techniques to identify database file formats, identify the table and format structures within the database, and extract or query the data contained in the database.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FEX	DSP	170	Methods and techniques to examine the contents of a binary file to determine functionality (both static and dynamic methods) and extract other case relevant data.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FEX	DSP	171	Methods and techniques to build a timeline from the data available from a file system forensic image, a memory image, or packet captures.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FEX	DSP	172	Methods and techniques to virtualise a forensic image and enable the booting of the forensic image as if it were an actual COMPUTER so that the COMPUTER can be observed in the same way the user thereof did.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FEX	DSP	173	Methods and techniques to identify internal file metadata and parse it out for examination.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FEX	DSP	174	Methods and techniques to identify encoded and obfuscated data strings, and methods and techniques to decode or deobfuscate the data strings.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FEX	DSP	175	Scripting to parse data from files and data structures.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FEX	DSP	176	Methods and techniques to decrypt encrypted volumes, folders and files.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FEX	DSP	177	Methods and techniques to extract folders, files, and data structures from a memory image.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FEX	DSP	178	Methods and techniques to parse file system structures and to navigate through a file system.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FEX	DSP	179	Methods and techniques to interact with a COMPUTER at a command line level.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FEX	DSP	180	Calculation of hash values from files, file fragments, DATA STRUCTURES within files or unallocated space using one-way hash algorithms (MD5, SHA, etc.).	6 Create	Create	Synthesise

KA	Sub	No.	Knowledge Topic Statement	BT Level	BT Cognitive Demand	BT Verb
FEX	DSP	181	Using hash data sets of known good, known malicious, and known contraband files, to exclude files, or identify files.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FEX	DSP	182	Obtaining the data available from COMPUTERS in a before first unlock state (BFU) or in an after first unlock state (AFU).	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FEX	IDE	183	Methods and techniques to identify encrypted files, files containing steganography data, alternate data streams, file extensions and type mismatches, and other concealed or hidden data.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FEX	IDE	184	Methods and techniques to identify known malicious and potentially malicious executable files.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FEX	IDE	185	Methods and techniques to identify the installed operating system, and default files and directory structures used by the identified operating system.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FEX	IDE	186	Methods and techniques to determine baseline normal activity within a COMPUTER or COMPUTER SYSTEM and contrast that to current activity within a COMPUTER or COMPUTER SYSTEM, to determine potentially abnormal activity.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FEX	IDE	187	Files and data structures that can identify that a user has used cloud storage services (accessed files, uploaded files, downloaded files, shared files, edited files, deleted files).	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FEX	IDE	188	Files and data structures that can identify that a user has used email (composed email, read email, sent email, set email rules, etc.).	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FEX	IDE	189	Files and data structures that can identify that an application had been executed, and where relevant, which account executed it.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FEX	IDE	190	Files and data structures that can identify the existence of a file or folder that is no longer present within the file system.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FEX	IDE	191	Files and data structures that can identify that a file or folder had been deleted by an account.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FEX	IDE	192	Files and folders that are typically installed and used by an operating system.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FEX	IDE	193	Files and data structures that can identify system configurations.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FEX	IDE	194	Files and data structures that can identify user preferences.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FEX	IDE	195	Files and data structures that can identify program installation.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FEX	IDE	196	Files and data structures that can identify Internet and other online activities by an account.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FEX	IDE	197	Files and data structures that can identify files that have been downloaded by an account.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise

KA	Sub	No.	Knowledge Topic Statement	BT Level	BT Cognitive Demand	BT Verb
FEX	IDE	198	Files and data structures that can identify account usage.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FEX	IDE	199	Files and data structures that can show network activity and communications between COMPUTERS.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FEX	IDE	200	Files and data structures that can identify timezone settings, and dates and file system timestamps of files and folders, and what caused these timestamps to be written or updated.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FEX	IDE	201	Files and data structures that can identify the actual or approximate physical location of a COMPUTER at a particular point in time.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FEX	IDE	202	Files and data structures that can identify external devices connected to the COMPUTER, when they were used, and what was accessed or transferred to them.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FEX	IDE	203	Files and data structures that can identify system events.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FEX	IDE	204	Files and data structures that can identify electronic communications between parties (email, internet chats, chat apps, video chats, phone calls, SMS, etc.).	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FEX	IDE	205	Files and data structures that can identify files moved between COMPUTERS via a network.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FEX	IDE	205	Files and data structures that can identify files moved between COMPUTERS via a network.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FEX	IDE	206	Files and data structures that can identify remote access between COMPUTERS via a network.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FEX	IDE	207	Files and data structures that can identify remote execution between COMPUTERS via a network.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FEX	IDE	208	Files and data structures that can identify synchronisation between COMPUTERS and online data sources, what was synchronised and when, and what COMPUTERS have been paired to each other.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FEX	IDE	224	Files and data structures that can identify the existence of an executable file that is no longer present within the file system.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FEX	IDE	225	Files and data structures that can identify that a file or folder had been accessed by an account.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise

DFS Forensic Analysis (12 topics)

Methods and techniques for the analysis, reconstruction, interpretation, and evaluation of digital evidence to answer forensic questions.

KA	Sub	No.	Knowledge Topic Statement	BT Level	BT Cognitive Demand	BT Verb
FAN	FAS	210	ISO 27042 Guidelines for the Analysis and Interpretation of Digital Evidence.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FAN	SCM	211	Methods and techniques to develop and test hypotheses using the scientific method.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FAN	SCM	212	Methods and techniques to conduct scientifically valid experimentation.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FAN	SCM	213	Methods and techniques to calculate and determine statistical validity and probability.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FAN	SCM	214	Methods and techniques to establish a level of confidence in the authenticity of any particular trace (including integrity and providence of the trace, contextual descriptions, and temporal restrictions).	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FAN	SCM	215	Methods and techniques to establish sufficient confidence that some identity-related information describes a specific entity or object in a given context, at a certain time.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FAN	SCM	216	Methods and techniques to develop taxonomies of traces and the decision process attempting to ascribe a trace with sufficient confidence to its class on the basis of characteristics that are common among traces of the same class, distinguishing them from traces of other classes.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FAN	EVM	217	Methods and techniques to organise observed traces to disclose the most likely operational conditions or capabilities (functional analysis), patterns in time (temporal analysis), and linkages between entities – people, places, objects (relational analysis).	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FAN	EVM	218	Methods and techniques to evaluate the evidence, to allow a decision process to be taken in relation to that evidence.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FAN	RAA	219	Reconstruction of past activity.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FAN	RAA	220	Methods and techniques to attribute activities on a COMPUTER or COMPUTER SYSTEM to an actual person.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise
FAN	RAA	221	Methods and techniques to determine intention.	6 Create	Create	Synthesise